

Research

A Simple Spectrofluorimetric Method for the Determination of Cadmium at Ultra-trace Levels in some Real, Environmental, Biological, Tobacco, Food, Fertilizer, and Soil Samples Using 2', 3, 4', 5, 7-pentahydroxyflavone

Abdul Hakim¹, Faisal Hossain¹, Israt Jahan¹, and M. Jamaluddin Ahmed^{1*},

¹Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, University of Chittagong, Chittagong-4331, University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

*Corresponding author

Accepted: 14 October, 2019; Online: 27 October, 2019

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3519939>

Abstract: A very simple, ultra-sensitive and highly selective non-extractive spectrofluorimetric method for the determination of cadmium at ultra-trace levels using 2',3,4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone(morin) has been developed. Morin reacts in a slightly acidic (0.0005-0.002 M H₂SO₄) aqueous solution with cadmium and to form intensely fluorescent chelate, which has high fluorescence intensity (λ_{ex} =424 nm; λ_{em} =485 nm).The reaction is instantaneous and the fluorescent intensely remains stable for the period between 5 min and 24 h. Linear calibration graphs were obtained for 0.01- 600- $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Cd, with an $R^2 = 0.99987$, having a detection limit of 1 ng L⁻¹; the quantification limit of the reaction system was found to be 10 ng L⁻¹ and the RSD was 0-3%. The stoichiometric composition of the chelate is 1:2 (Cd: morin). A large excess of over 60 captions, anions and complexing agents (like chloride, phosphate, azide, tartrate, oxalate, SCN⁻ etc.) do not interfere in the determination. The developed method was successfully used in the determination of cadmium in several Standard Reference Materials (alloys, steels, sediments, human hair, bovine liver, freshwater, and rice flour) as well as in some environmental waters (potable and polluted), biological samples (human blood, urine and hair), tobacco samples, food samples (rice, wheat, cake, tea, cookies and shellfish), vegetables samples (radish, carrot, ginger, potato, tomato and cabbage), fertilizer samples, soil samples and complex synthetic mixtures. The results of the biological, food and vegetable analyses by spectrofluorimetric methods were found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS. The method has high precision and accuracy ($s = \pm 0.01$ for 0.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

Keywords: Spectrofluorimetry; cadmium determination; morin.

Introduction

The spectrofluorimetric method for the determination of rare earth elements has long been recognized in recent years (Gao, Zhao, & Kang, 1995); increasing attention has been focused on pollution of the environment. Particular attention is being paid to the heavy metals because of their irreversible effects on health. Cadmium is one of the most important heavy metal pollutants. It is an extremely toxic metal (Christensen & Olson, 1957) and symptoms of cadmium poisoning include instantaneous hypertension (Mitchell Perry Jr & Yunice, 1965) shortening of life-span, kidney damage, bronchitis, retardation of growth, gross abnormalities of the vital organs, alopecia (loss of hair), diabetes, diarrhea, nausea, liver injury anemia, renal cancer in human and the risk of prostatic cancer (Kjellström, Friberg, & Rahnster, 1979). One example of acute cadmium poisoning is the disease Itai-Itai, which causes gradual weakening of the bone structure, diminution of stature and ultimately the total collapse of the entire skeletal system (Schroeder, 1971). It also causes generalized cancers in laboratory animals and has been linked epidemiologically with certain human cancers (Fergusson, 1990). Its extreme toxicity towards marine and freshwater organisms is also well known; the lethal level for *Daphnia*, for example, is around $2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Increasing cadmium pollution of the environment resulting from the growth of cadmium-based industries and the use of fossil fuels. Again cadmium is a potential health hazard due to its presence in an urban atmosphere and cigarette smoke (Ahmed, Zannat, & Fatema, 2014). On the other hand, the nutrient role of the metal ion has also recently been recognized and cadmium deficiency in goats caused myasthenia (Nielsen, 1984). All these findings cause great concern regarding public health, demanding accurate determination of this metal ion at trace and ultra-trace levels. Many sensitive techniques such as X-ray fluorescence, Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA), AAS, Graphite furnace atomic absorption spectroscopy (GF-AAS), Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Pulsepolarography, Spectrophotometry, and Spectrofluorimetry have been widely applied to the determination of cadmium. However, the spectrofluorimetric method still has the advantages of being simple and without requiring expensive or complicated test equipment. For this reason, a wide variety of spectrofluorimetric methods for the determination of cadmium has been developed. Several authors have reported on the extractive spectrofluorimetric determination of cadmium using complexes formed variety of reagents (Bijoli Kanti Pal, Kabiraj, & Ukiluddin, 1987). In most of the methods, cadmium forms soluble or insoluble complexes with reagents with various organic solvents for spectrofluorimetric determination. Most of these reagents are expensive and non-recoverable. Most of the organic solvents which were used are carcinogenic. We, therefore, searched for much better fluorometric reagent. Hydroxyflavones are probably the most widely used fluorimetric reagents in inorganic trace analysis, but a recent literature survey, including excellent reviews indicated that none have been applied to cadmium except

Pal *et al.* (Bijoli Kanti Pal *et al.*, 1987), which is less sensitive, pH-dependent fluorescence stable only a few minutes (45min) using γ -picoline for complexation and less selective due to much interference hence it is not suitable for any routine analysis.

The aim of this study was to develop a simpler direct spectrofluorimetric method for the ultra-trace determination of cadmium. In the search for a more sensitive reagent, 2',3,4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone (morin) and cadmium forms an intensely fluorescent chelate product. The method possesses distinct advantages over existing methods with respect to sensitivity, selectivity, range of determination, simplicity, speed, pH /acidity range, thermal stability, accuracy, precision and ease of operation. The method is based on the Fluorescence complex formation reaction of non-fluorescent morin in a slightly acidic (0.0005-0.002 M H₂SO₄) solution with cadmium to produce a highly fluorescent product, followed by direct measurement of the fluorescence intensity in an absolutely aqueous solution at room temperature (25±5°C). With suitable masking, the reaction can be made to be highly selective and the reagent blank solutions show negligible fluorescence at these wavelengths.

Experimental Section

Apparatus

A Shimadzu (Kyoto, Japan) (Model-RF-5301PC) Spectrofluorophotometer and a Jenway (England, UK) (Model-3010) pH meter with a combination of electrodes were used for measurements of the fluorescence intensity and pH, respectively. A Thermo Fisher Scientific (Model-iCE 3000, origin USA) atomic absorption spectrophotometer equipped with a microcomputer-controlled nitrous oxide-acetylene flame was used to compare the results. The infrared spectrum was recorded with FTIR Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu (Model-IR Prestige, Detector-DTGS KBr) in the range 7500-350 cm⁻¹ to test the purity of the morin.

Reagents and solutions

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade of the highest purity available. High-purity distilled absolute ethanol and high-purity double-distilled de-ionized water was used throughout. High-purity water was obtained by passing tap water through cellulose absorbent and to mixed-bed ion exchange columns, followed by distillation in a corning AG-11 unit. Glass vessel was cleaned by soaking in acidified solutions of KMnO₄ or K₂Cr₂O₇ followed by washing with concentrated HNO₃ and rinsed several times with high purity de-ionized water. Stock solutions and environmental water samples (1000 mL each) were kept in polypropylene bottles containing 1mL concentrated HNO₃. More rigorous contamination control was used when the cadmium levels in the specimens were low.

Morin Solution (3×10^{-4} M): The reagent solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount (0.0023 g) of morin (BDH chemicals, pro analysis grade, 99.5%), in a known volume (25 mL) of distilled absolute ethanol. More dilute solutions of the reagent were prepared as and when required. A freshly prepared reagent (morin) solution (10^{-5} M) was used whenever as required. The purity of the morin was tested by taking the melting point, an FTIR spectrum, and thermogravimetric analysis. The melting point of the reagent (morin) was $300 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (lit. $300\text{-}303^\circ\text{C}$). The FTIR spectrum of the reagent (morin) is as shown in **Fig.1**. The presence of a peak at 1625.35 in **Fig.1** was due to the characteristic C=O double bond peak ($\nu^{\text{C=O}}$, $1612\text{-}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$), The peak at 1560.26 in **Fig.1** was due to the characteristic C=C double bond peak ($\nu^{\text{C=C}}$, $1527\text{-}1591\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The peak at 1285.52 in **Fig.1** was due to the characteristic C=O double bond peak ($\nu^{\text{C=O}}$, $1260\text{-}1326\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the morin. Both the melting point and FTIR spectral analysis data indicated the purity of the reagent (morin). The steadiness of the thermogravimetric curve obtained for about 1g of the reagent at $80\text{-}90^\circ\text{C}$, which indicates that the reagent did not contain any moisture, is shown in **Fig.2**.

Cadmium standard solution (8.896×10^{-3} M): A 100-ml amount of stock solution (1 mg mL^{-1}) of divalent cadmium was prepared by dissolving 179.23 mg of purified-grade (Aldrich A.C.S. grade) hydrated cadmium chloride ($\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) in doubly distilled de-ionized water and aliquots of this solution were standardized by EDTA titration using xylenol orange as an indicator (Vogel & Jeffery, 1989). More dilute standard solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of aliquots from the stock solution with de-ionized water as and when required. A freshly standardized solution was always used.

Potassium permanganate solution: A 1% potassium permanganate (Merck) solution was prepared by dissolving in de-ionized water. Aliquots of this solution were standardized with oxalic acid. Sodium azide solution (2.5% w/v) (Fluka purity > 99%) was also used.

Tartrate solution: A 100 mL stock solution of tartrate (0.01 % w/v) was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of A.C.S.-grade (99%) potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate in (100 mL) de-ionized water.

Aqueous ammonia solution: A 100 mL solution of an aqueous ammonia solution was prepared by diluting 10 mL concentrated NH_4OH (28-30%, A.C.S.-grade) to 100 mL with de-ionized water. The solution was stored in a polypropylene bottle.

Fig .1.FTIR spectrum of 2',3,4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone (morin)

Fig.2. Thermogravimetric curve of 2',3,4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone(morin) at 80-90°C.

Other Solutions

Solutions of a large number of inorganic ions and complexing agents were prepared from their AnalaR grade or equivalent grade water-soluble salts (or the oxides and carbonates in hydrochloric acid); those of niobium, tantalum, titanium, zirconium, and hafnium were specially prepared from their corresponding oxides (Specpure, Johnson Matthey) according to the recommended procedures of Mukharjee (Mukherji, 1970). In the case of insoluble substances, special dissolution methods were adopted (Bijoli K Pal & Chaudhury, 1985).

Procedure

To 0.1-1.0 mL of a neutral aqueous solution containing 0.1-6000 ng of cadmium in a 10-mL calibrated flask was mixed with a 1:30-1:150 fold molar excess of the 2',3,4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone (morin) reagent solution (preferably 1 mL of 3×10^{-5} M) followed by the addition of 0.3-1.5 mL (preferably 1 mL) of 0.001 M of sulfuric acid. The solution was mixed well and allowed to stand for 5 min and the volume was made up to the mark with de-ionized water.

The fluorescence intensity of the system was measured at 485 nm against a corresponding reagent blank, prepared concurrently, keeping the excitation wavelength maximum at 424 nm and the instrument setting the same. The cadmium content in an unknown sample was determined using a concurrently prepared calibration graph.

Sample collection and preservation

Environmental samples: Water samples were collected in polythene bottles from different places of Bangladesh. After collection, HNO_3 (1 mL L^{-1}) was added as a preservative.

Blood and Urine: Blood and urine samples were collected in polythene bottles from effected persons of Chittagong Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh. Samples were collected with the consent of the patient and also with the permission of the doctor. Immediately after collection, they were stored in a salt-ice mixture and later, at the laboratory, were at 20°C in a refrigerator.

Tobacco and cigarette: Tobacco and cigarette samples were collected from the local market, Chittagong and homogenized with a mortar.

Food samples: Food samples (rice, wheat, tea, and vegetables) were collected from the local market of Chittagong. After collection of the samples (rice, wheat, tea, fish and vegetables) were stored in the refrigerator for preservation. Samples (rice, wheat, tea) were used as dry conditions and homogenized with a mortar.

Fertilizer samples: Fertilizer samples of different varieties were collected from the local market of Chittagong. Samples were homogenized with a mortar.

Soil samples: Soil samples were collected from different locations of Bangladesh. Samples were dried in air and homogenized with a mortar.

Results and Discussion

Factors Affecting the Fluorescence Intensity

Spectral characteristics

The excitation and emission spectra of the fluorescent Cd-Morin in 0.001M sulfuric acid medium

was recorded using the spectrofluorometer. The excitation and emission maxima were at 424 nm and 485 nm, respectively. The reagent blank exhibited negligible fluorescence, despite having a wavelength maximum in the same region. In all instances, measurements were made against the reagent blank. The spectra are shown in **Fig.3**. The structure of the reagent is shown in **Scheme-I**.

Scheme- I. Structure of 2',3,4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone (morin).

Fig. 3. A and B, Excitation spectra of the Cd-morin system and the reagent blank, respectively ($\lambda_{ex}=424$ nm); and C and D are the corresponding emission spectra ($\lambda_{em}=485$ nm).

Effect of acidity

Of the various acids (nitric, sulfuric, hydrochloric and phosphoric) studied, sulfuric acid was found to be the best acid for the system. The fluorescence intensity was at maximum and constant when the 10mL of solution ($10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Cd) contained 0.5-2 mL of 0.001M sulfuric acid at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). Outside this range of acidity, the fluorescence intensity decreased (**Fig.4**). The optimum acidity range in the final solution is, therefore, 0.0005-0.002M H_2SO_4 . For all subsequent measurements, 1 mL of 0.001 M sulfuric acid was added.

Effect of temperature

The Cd-morin system attained maximum and constant fluorescence intensity at 15-40°C temperature. For all subsequent measurements were done at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$).

Fig.4. Effect of acidity on the fluorescence of Cd-morin system

Effect of time

The reaction is instantaneous. The Cd-morin system attained maximum and constant fluorescence intensity immediately (within 5 min) after dilution of the solution to the final volume, which then remained strictly unaltered for 24 h at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) shown in **Fig.5**.

Effect of reagent concentration

Different molar excesses of morin were added to a fixed metal ion concentration and fluorescence intensities were measured according to the standard procedure. It was observed that at $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ cadmium and the reagent molar ratios of 1:30 - 1:150 produced a constant fluorescence intensity of the Cd-chelate (**Fig.6**). Greater excesses of reagents were not studied. At different cadmium concentrations (0.5 and $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), the effect of varying the reagent concentration was similar. For all subsequent measurements, 1 mL of 3×10^{-5} M morin reagent was added.

Fig.5. Effect of the time on the fluorescence of the Cd-morin system.

Calibration graph (Beer's law and sensitivity)

The well-known equation for spectrofluorimetric analysis in very dilute solutions derived from Beer's law. The effect of metal concentration was studied over $0.001-1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ distributed in six different sets ($0.001-0.01$, $0.01-0.1$, $0.1-1$, $1-10$, $10-100$ and $100-1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) for convenience of measurement. The fluorescence intensity was linear over a wide range [10pg mL^{-1} to 600ng mL^{-1} for $0.01-600 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$] of cadmium at an excitation wavelength at 424nm and emission wavelength at 485nm representing five linear graphs ($0.01-0.1$, $0.1-1.0$, $1-10$, $10-100$ and $100-600 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Of five calibration graphs, the one showing the limit of the linearity range (**Fig.7**). The limit of detection and limit of quantitation were found to be 1pg mL^{-1} and 10pg mL^{-1} , respectively. The selected analytical parameters obtained with the optimization experiments are summarized in **Table 1**.

Fig.6. Effect of reagent (Cd: morin molar concentration ratio) on the fluorescence of Cd– morin system.

Fig.7. Calibration graph E: 100-1000 µgL⁻¹ of cadmium. Bandwidth: Ex.slit-3, Em.slit-3

Table 1. Selected analytical parameters obtained with the optimization experiments.

Parameters	Studied range	Selected value
Excitation wavelength maximum / λ_{ex} (nm)	200-800	424
Emission wavelength maximum/ λ_{em} (nm)	200-800	485
Acidity / M H ₂ SO ₄	0.0001-0.075	0.0005-0.002 (Preferably 0.001)
pH	3.0-1.130	3.0-2.40 (Preferably 1.0)
Time / h	0 - 72	1min - 24 h (Preferably 5 min)
Temperature / °C	10-70	15-40 (Preferably 25 ± 5)
Reagent (fold molar excess, M:R)	1:5 - 1:160	1:30 - 1:150 (Preferably 1:50)
Linear range/ $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	0.001-1000	0.01- 600
Limit of quantitation/ ng L^{-1}	1-100	10
Detection limit/ ng L^{-1}	0.01-10	1
Reproducibility (% RSD)	0 - 10	0 -3
Regression Co-efficient (R^2)	0.9992-0.9999	0.99987

Effect of Foreign Ions

More than 60 anions, cations, and complexing agents were studied individually to investigate their effect on the determination of $1\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of cadmium. The criterion for an interference (Ojeda, De Torres, Rojas, & Pavon, 1987) was a fluorescence intensity value varying by more than $\pm 5\%$ from the expected value for cadmium alone. The results are summarized in **Table.2**. As can be seen, a large number of ions have no significant effect on the determination of cadmium. The most serious

interference was from Al(III) and Fe(II) ions. Interference from these ions is probably due to complex formation with morin. The greater tolerance limits for these ions can be achieved by using several masking agents. In order to eliminate the interference of Al(III) and Fe(II) ions, EDTA and tartrate can be used as masking agents, respectively (Bijoli Kanti Pal, Singh, & Dutta, 1992). A 50 and 100-fold excess of Al(III) and Fe(II) ions could be masked with EDTA and tartrate, respectively. These two ions were masked because Al(III) and Fe(II) would probably form complexes with EDTA and tartrate, respectively. During the interference studies, if a precipitate was formed, it was removed by centrifugation. The amount mentioned is not the tolerance limit but the actual amount studied. However, for those ions whose tolerance limits have been studied, their tolerance ratios are mentioned in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Table of tolerance limits of foreign ions^a, tolerance ratio [species(x) /Cd (w/w)]

Species x	Tolerance ratio x/Cd(w/w)	Species x	Tolerance ratio x/Cd (w/w)
Ammonium	1000	Lithium	200c
Arsenic(III)	200	Lead	500
Arsenic(V)	200	Magnesium	500
Aluminium	50b	Manganese(II)	1000
Azide	1000	Manganese(VII)	200
Ascorbic acid	1000	Mercury(II)	500
Antimony	500	Molybdenum(VI)	500c
Bromide	1000	Nitrate	1000
Bismuth(III)	200b	Nickel	200c
Beryllium	1000	Oxalate	1000
Calcium	200b	Potassium	1000

Chloride	1000	Phosphate	200
Cobalt (II)	200	Selenium (IV)	500
Cobalt(III)	500	Selenium(VI)	500
Chromium(III)	500	Silver	1000
Chromium(VI)	200	Sodium	1000
Carbonate	1000	Strontium	1000
Cesium	1000	Sulfate	500
Citrate	1000	Titanium(IV)	500
Cerium(III)	1000	Tellurium(IV)	500
Cerium(IV)	500	Tartrate	1000
Copper(II)	500	Thiocyanate	1000
Cyanide	500b	Thiourea	500
EDTA	1000	Tungsten(VI)	500b
Fluoride	1000	Tin(II)	500
Iodide	1000	Tin(IV)	1000
Iron (II)	100c	Vanadium(V)	500
Iron (III)	500c	Zinc	500

^a Tolerance limit was defined as a ratio that causes less than ± 5 percent interference.

^b with 10 mg L^{-1} EDTA

^c with 10 mg L^{-1} tartrate.

Composition of the Flourescent Complex (Stoichiometry of the complex)

Job's method (Job, 1928) of continuous variation and the molar ratio method (Yoe & Jones, 1944) were applied to ascertain the stoichiometric composition of the complex under the optimum conditions (**Table 1**). A Cd-morin (1:2) complex was indicated by both methods (**Fig.8**). Experimental data has been presented graphically in **Fig.8** and the stoichiometry was found to be 1:2 (Cd: morin). Referring to this data, it can be concluded the complex formed in an absolutely aqueous medium, is in the form of $[Cd(2', 3, 4', 5, 7- \text{pentahydroxyflavone})_2]$ the probable structure is shown in **Scheme-II**.

Scheme- II. The probable structure of $[Cd(2', 3, 4', 5, 7- \text{pentahydroxyflavone})_2]$

Fig.8. Job's method for determining the composition of the Cd: morin (1:2) complex

Precision and Accuracy

The precision of the present method was evaluated by determining different concentrations of cadmium (each analyzed at least five times). The relative standard deviation (n=5) was 3-0% for 0.1-6000 ng of cadmium in 10-mL, indicating that this method is highly precise and reproducible, **Table 1**. The detection limit (3s of the blank) and limit of quantitation (10 times of detection limit) for cadmium were found to be 1 ng L⁻¹ and 10 ng L⁻¹, respectively. The method was tested by analyzing several synthetic mixtures containing cadmium and diverse ions, **Table 3**. The method was applied in a number of real samples; the results for total cadmium were in good agreement with certified values **Table 4**. The reliability of our cadmium-chelate procedure was tested by recovery studies. The average percentage recovery obtained for the addition of cadmium spike to some environmental water samples was quantitative, as shown in **Table 5**. The results of biological analyses by the spectrofluorimetric method were in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS, **Table 6**. The results of food analyses by spectrofluorimetric method were also

found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS, **Table 8**. Hence, the precision and accuracy of the method were found to be excellent.

Applications

The present method was successfully applied to the determination of cadmium in a series of synthetic mixtures of various compositions and also in a number of real samples e.g. several Certified Reference Materials (CRMs). The method was also extended to the determination of cadmium in a number of environmental, biological, tobacco, food, vegetable, fertilizer, and soil samples. In view of the unknown composition of environmental water samples, the same equivalent portions of each such sample were analyzed for cadmium content; the recoveries in both the “spiked” (added to the samples before the mineralization or dissolution) and the “unspiked” samples are in excellent agreement. The results of biological analyses by the spectrofluorimetric method were found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS. The results of food and vegetable analyses by the spectrofluorimetric method were also found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS. Hence the precision and accuracy of the method were excellent.

Determination of cadmium in some synthetic mixtures

Several synthetic mixtures of varying compositions containing Cadmium and diverse ions of known concentrations were determined by the present method using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent. The results were found to be highly reproducible as shown in **Table 3**. Accurate recoveries were achieved in all solutions.

Determination of cadmium in some certified reference materials

A 0.1-g amount of an alloy or steel sample containing 1.9 -7.0 % of cadmium was weighed accurately and placed in a 50 mL Erlenmeyer flask following a method recommended by Parker (Parker, 1986). To it, 10 mL of 20% sulfuric acid was added while carefully covering with a watch glass until the brisk reaction subsided. The solution was heated and simmered gently after the addition of 10 mL of concentrated HNO₃ until all carbides were decomposed.

Table 3. Determination of cadmium in some synthetic mixtures

Sample	Composition of mixtures ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Cadmium/ $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		
		Added	Found ^a (n=5)	Recovery \pm SD ^b (%)
A	Cd	10	9.98	99.8 \pm 0.5
		50	50.0	100.0 \pm 0.0
B	A + Na(50) + As ³⁺ (50) + Ba(50) + Co ²⁺ (50) + Zn(50)	10	9.99	99.9 \pm 0.6
		50	49.98	99.96 \pm 0.8
C	B + Bi ³⁺ (50) + K(50) + Ti ⁴⁺ (50) + Ni(50) + Ca(50)	10	9.97	99.7 \pm 1.0
		50	49.96	99.9 \pm 1.2
D	C + Cr ³⁺ (50) + Se ⁴⁺ (50) + Se ⁶⁺ (50) + Fe ³⁺ (50) + Al(50) + Hg ²⁺ (50) + EDTA(50)	10	9.96	99.6 \pm 1.5
		50	49.95	99.9 \pm 1.8
E	D + Ag(50) + Li(50) + Mn ²⁺ (50) + W ⁶⁺ (50) + Mg(50)	10	9.94	99.4 \pm 2.0
		50	49.90	99.8 \pm 2.5

^a Average of five analyses of each sample.

^b The measure of precision is the standard deviation (SD).

Then, 2 mL of 1:1 (v/v) H₂SO₄ was added and the solution was carefully evaporated to dense white fumes to drive off the oxides of nitrogen, and then cooled to room temperature (25 \pm 5)⁰C. After suitable dilution with de-ionized water, the contents of the Erlenmeyer flask were warmed so as to dissolve the soluble salts. The solution was then cooled and neutralized with a dilute NH₄OH in the presence of 1-2 ml of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The resulting solution was filtered, if necessary, through a Whatman No. 40 filter paper into a 100 mL calibrated flask. The residue (silica and tungstenic acid) was washed with a small volume of hot (1+99) H₂SO₄, followed by water; the volume was made up to the mark with de-ionized water.

A suitable aliquot (1-2 mL) of the above-mentioned solution was taken into a 10mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under Procedure using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent. The proposed procedure for the spectrofluorimetric determination of cadmium was applied to the analysis of estuarine sediment (SRM-1646a), human hair (CRM-397), freshwater (NIST-SRM -132228), bovine liver (NIST-SRM 1577a), and rice flour (NBS-SRM-15680), CRMs obtained from The National Research Council of Canada, using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent, following a method recommended by Sun *et al* (Sun, Yang, & Tzeng, 1999). Based on five replicate analyses, average cadmium concentration determined by our general procedure. The validity of our method was tested by analyzing several certified reference materials (CRMs) of different compositions. The results for cadmium found were in excellent agreement with those of the certified values. The results were highly reproducible. The results are shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Determination of cadmium in some certified reference materials.

Sample	Certified reference materials (Composition %)	Cadmium (%)		
		In C.R.M sample	Found (n=5)	RSD ^a
1	GBWO 169 ^b : Unalloyed Steel: (Ag=3.5; As=17; Bi=4.2; Ca=42; Cd=7.0; Ga=29; In=11; Mg=82; Pb=12; Sb=20.4; Sc=43; Sn=10.3; Ti=8.5; Zn=24)	7.0	6.98±0.02	1.0
2	GBW 01620 ^b : Unalloyed Steel: (Ag=4.6; As=11; Bi=0.4; Ca=21; Cd=4.6; Ga=32; Mg=16; Pb=4.1; Sb=95; Se=16; Sn=53; Ti=22; Zn=32)	4.6	4.57±0.01	1.5
3	GBW 01622 ^b : Unalloyed Steel: (Ag=0.3; As=72; Bi=0.5; Ca=22; Cd=1.9; Sb=7.4; Ga=28; In=0.4; Mg=53; Pb=2.2; Se=43; Sn=0.10; Ti=83; Zn=20)	1.9	2.0±0.009	2.0

4	CRM-397:Human hair ^c	0.521±0.024	0.519±0.018	2.5
5	SRM-1646a:Estuarinesediment ^d	148.0	147.5±0.5	1.0
6	NIST-SRM-132228: Fresh water ^d	100.0±0.072	102.0±0.075	2.0
7	NIST-SRM-1577a: Bovine liver ^d	440.0±0.014	442.0±0.015	2.5
8	NBS-SRM-1568: Rice flour ^d	29.0	28.5±0.5	1.5

^a The measure of precision is the relative standard deviation (RSD).

^b These CRMs were from Beijing NCS Analytical Instruments CO. Ltd. China.

^c Values in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$

^d Values in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$

Determination of cadmium in some environmental water samples

Each filtered (with Whatman No. 40) environmental water sample (25 mL contained in a 50 mL Pyrex beaker) was evaporated nearly to dryness with a mixture of 1-mL concentrated H_2SO_4 and 5 mL of concentrated HNO_3 in a fume cupboard, following a method recommended by Greenberg *et al* (Greenberg, Clesceri, & Eaton, 1992). And was then cooled to room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). The residue was then heated with 10 mL de-ionized water in order to dissolve the salts. The solution was then cooled and neutralized with dilute NH_4OH solution in the presence of 1-2 mL of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The resulting solution was then filtered and quantitatively transferred into a 25 mL calibrated flask and made up to the mark with deionized water. An aliquot (1-2 mL) of this digested water sample was pipetted into a 10-mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under the Procedure using EDTA or tartrate as masking agent. The analyses of environmental water samples from various sources of cadmium are shown in **Table 5**. Most spectrofluorimetric methods for determination of cadmium in natural and seawater require preconcentration of cadmium. The concentration of cadmium in natural water and seawater is a few $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in developed countries. The mean concentration of cadmium found in U.S. drinking water is 10-100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

Determination of cadmium in some biological samples

Human blood (1-2 mL) or urine (5-10 mL) or hair (1-2 g) was taken into a 100-mL micro-Kjeldahl flask. A glass bead and 10-mL of concentrated nitric acid were added, and the flask was placed on the digester under gentle heating. The sample was digested in the presence of an oxidizing agent solution according to the method recommended by Stahr (Stahr & Stahr, 1991). When the initial brisk reaction was completed, the solution was removed and cooled to room temperature ($25\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$). A 1 mL volume of concentrated sulfuric acid was carefully added and heating was continued to dense white fumes of sulfur trioxide, while repeating the nitric acid addition, if necessary. Heating was continued for at least 0.5 h for complete digestion and then cooling was applied. The content of the flask was filtered and neutralized with dilute NH_4OH solution in presence of 1-2 mL of a 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The resultant solution was then filtered and transferred into a 25 mL calibrated flask and made up to the mark with deionized water.

A suitable aliquot (1-2mL) of the final solution was pipetted out into a 10-mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under general Procedure using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent. The results of biological analyses by the spectrofluorimetric method were found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS. The results are shown in **Table 6**.

The abnormally high value for the kidney disease patient is probably due to the involvement of high cadmium concentrations with Cu and Zn. The occurrences of such high cadmium content are also reported in kidney disease patients from some developed countries (Hygienists, 1995).

Table 5. Determination of cadmium in some environmental water samples

Sample	Cadmium/ $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$		Recovery \pm s (%)	s_r^b (%)	
	Added	Found ^a (n=5)			
Tap water (Chittagong city)	0	10.8	100.0 \pm 0.0	0.00	
	10	20.8	102.8 \pm 0.5	0.21	
	50	62.5			
Well water (Chittagong city)	0	15.0	100.0 \pm 0.0	0.00	
	10	25.0	104.6 \pm 0.8	0.35	
	50	68.0			
River water	Karnaphully (upper)	0	25.0	100.0 \pm 0.0	0.00
		10	35.0	104.0 \pm 0.6	0.29
		50	78.0		
	Karnaphully (lower)	0	28.5	100.0 \pm 0.0	0.00
		10	38.5	101.9 \pm 0.6	0.36
		50	80.0		
	Halda (upper)	0	15.5	100.0 \pm 0.0	0.00
		10	25.5	101.9 \pm 0.5	0.31
		50	66.8		
	Halda (lower)	0	17.0	100.0 \pm 0.0	0.00
		10	27.0	101.5 \pm 0.7	0.39
		50	68.0		

Seawater	Bay of Bengal (upper)	0	6.5	101.8±0.8	0.18
		10	16.8	102.3±0.6	0.27
		50	57.8		
	Bay of Bengal (lower)	0	7.8	98.3±0.3	0.25
		10	17.5	100.3±0.5	0.29
		50	58.0		
Drain water	T. S. P. Complex ^c	0	45.0	100.0 ± 0.0	0.00
		10	55.0	105.3±0.8	0.45
		50	100.0		
	PHP ^d	0	50.0	101.7±0.6	0.25
		10	61.0	105.0±0.5	0.21
		50	105.0		
	BSRM ^e	0	125.0	100.0±0.0	0.00
		10	135.0	101.7±0.4	0.16
		50	178.0		
	K.P.M Water ^f	0	120.0	100.0±0.0	0.00
		10	130.0	101.2±0.8	0.35
		50	172.0		
Eastern refinery ^g	0	130.0	100.0±0.0	0.00	
	10	140.0	102.8±0.9	0.48	
	50	185.0			

^a Average of five replicate determinations of each sample.

^b The measured precision is the relative standard deviation(s_r).

^c T. S. P. Complex Ltd., Patenga, Chittagong.

^d PHP Float Glass Industries, Kumira, Sitakunda, Chittagong.

^e Bangladesh Steel Re-rolling Mills Ltd.(BSRM), BaizidBosthami, Chittagong.

^fKarnaphuly Paper Mills, Chandraghona, Chittagong.

^gEastern refinery, North Patenga, Chittagong.

Table 6. Determination results of cadmium for human fluids and hair

Serial No.	Sample	Cadmium/ $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$				Sample Source ^a
		AAS (n=5)		Proposed method (n = 5)		
		Found	RSD (%)	Found	RSD (%)	
1	Blood	225.8	1.0	226.0	1.0	Kidney disease patient (Male)
	Urine	58.5	1.5	60.5	1.3	
2	Blood	145.0	1.5	150.0	1.3	Hypertension patient (Female)
	Urine	38.0	1.6	40.0	1.5	
3	Blood	215.0	1.6	218.0	1.5	Oesophagus cancer patient. (Female)
	Urine	55.0	1.5	56.5	1.8	
4	Blood	195.5	1.8	198.8	1.6	Liver cirrhosis patient (Male)
	Urine	49.0	2.0	50.5	1.8	
5	Blood	75.0	2.0	78.5	2.5	Diabetes patient (Male)
	Urine	19.0	1.8	20.5	2.0	
6	Blood	68.5	2.3	70.5	2.3	Smoker(Male)
	Urine	18.5	2.0	19.8	2.1	

7	Blood	5.0	1.2	4.9	1.5	Normal adult(Male) Non-smoker
	Urine	2.0	1.5	1.55	1.8	
8	Human hair ^b	63.5	2.0	65.8	1.8	Normal human hair (Male)

^a Samples were from Chittagong Medical College Hospital. (with prior permission the authority)

^b Values in ng g⁻¹ or µg kg⁻¹.

Determination of cadmium in some tobacco and cigarette

Tobacco or tobacco of cigarette (1.0 g) was accurately weighed and placed in a 100-mL micro-Kjeldahl flask. The sample was dissolved in 10 mL of concentrated HNO₃ and heating about dryness. The content of the flask was filtered through a Whatman No. 40 filter paper into a 25 mL calibrated flask and neutralized with dilute NH₄OH solution in presence of 1-2 mL of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The resulting solution was then filtered and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water (Ahmed et al., 2014). A suitable aliquot (1-2 mL) of the final solution was pipetted out into a 10-mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under procedure using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent. The cadmium content was then determined by the above procedure and quantified from a calibration graph prepared concurrently. The results are shown in **Table 7**. In our analysis the highest cadmium was found in the Gold-Leaf cigarette. A single cigarette typically contains 1-2 µg of cadmium. When burned, cadmium is present at a level of 1000-3000 µg m⁻³ in the smoke. Approximately 40-60 % of the cadmium inhaled from cigarette smoke is able to pass through the lungs and into the body. This means that for each cigarette smoked, a person can absorb an additional 1-3 µg of cadmium over

what is taken in from other sources in their daily life. Smokers typically have twice as much as cadmium in their bodies as their nonsmoking counterparts. As a result, smokers are highly at risk of liver and kidney damage and other cadmium poisoning diseases.

Table 7. Determination of cadmium in some tobacco and cigarette samples.

Cadmium			
Serial	ng/Cigarette		Sample/ Brand Name
No.	Found	RSD%	
	(n=5)		
S ₁	2.98±0.06 ^a	2.0	Whole tobacco
S ₂	295.0±1.2	1.6	Gold-leaf
S ₃	245.0±1.5	2.0	Benson
S ₄	175.0±1.8	2.8	Navy

^aValues in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$

Determination of cadmium in some food samples

The food samples used were rice, cake, cookies, tea, and shellfish and these were used under dry conditions. Each sample was first ground in a mortar. The samples (1.0 g) were weighed accurately and placed in a porcelain crucible and charred in an electric furnace; the sample was ashed at 555° C in a muffle furnace, following a method recommended by Stahr. 2.0 mL of HCl and 10 ml of water were added to the ash. The mixture of each foodstuff was heated below the boiling point for a moment. The solution was then cooled and neutralized with dilute NH₄OH in presence of 1-2mL of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution and filtered. The resulting solution was quantitatively transferred into a 25-mL calibrated flask and mixed well and made up to the mark with deionized water. A suitable aliquot (1-2mL) of the final solution was pipetted out into a 10 mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under Procedure using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent. The results of food analyses by the spectrofluorimetric method were also found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS. The results are shown in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Determination of cadmium in some food samples from the local market of Chittagong.

Serial No.	Sample	Cadmium/mg kg ⁻¹			
		Found ^a ± s			
		AAS (n=5)		Proposed Method	
		Found	RS ^b	Found	RSD ^b
1	Rice flour (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	0.029±0.005	1.0	0.0285±0.008	1.2
2	Wheat flour (<i>Triticumaestivum</i>)	0.26± 0.05	1.2	0.265±0.6	1.3
3	Tea leaves (<i>Camellia sinensis</i>)	0.03 ± 0.005	0.5	0.055±0.006	0.8
4	Choclote cake	10.5 ± 1.0	2.5	10.3 ± 1.0	2.8
5	Salten cookies	2.5 ± 0.005	1.3	2.49 ± 0.06	1.5
6	Shellfish (Prawn) (<i>Macrobrachiumrosenbergii</i>)	225.0	2.5	228.0	2.3

^a Average of five replicate analyses of each sample.

^b The measure of precision is the relative standard deviation (RSD).

Determination of cadmium in some vegetable samples

The vegetable samples collected prior to the determination were pretreated in the following way: Edible portion of samples was first washed and clean with tap water followed by rewashing with deionized water. After removing deionized water from the surface of vegetables the samples were cut into small pieces and dried at 65° C in oven. An airdried vegetable samples (10gm) were taken in a 100- mL micro - kjeldahl flask and digested following a method recommended by Stahr⁹⁰ and 10 mL of concentrated nitric acid were added and the flask was placed on the digester under gentle heating. When the initial brisk reaction was over, the solution was removed and cooled at room

temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). 1 mL volume of concentrated sulfuric acid was added carefully, and heating was continued for at least 0.5 h to form white fumes and then cooled and neutralized with dilute NH_4OH in presence of 1-2mL of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The resulting solution was filtered and quantitatively transferred into a 25- mL calibrated flask and mixed well and made up to the mark with deionized water. A suitable aliquot (1-2mL) of the final solution was pipetted out into a 10 mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under Procedure using EDTA or tartrate as a masking agent. The results of vegetable analyses by the spectrofluorimetric method were also found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by AAS. The results are shown in **Table 9**. The high value of cadmium for *daucus carota* (carrot) is probably due to the involvement of the high cadmium concentration in the soil.

Table 9. Determination of cadmium in some vegetable samples.

Serial No.	Sample	Cadmium/mg kg ⁻¹			
		Found ^a ± s (n=5)			
		AAS (n=5)		Proposed Method	
		Found	RSD ^b	Found	RSD ^b
1	Radish (<i>Raphanus sativus</i>)	2.2 ± 0.2	1.0	2.3 ± 0.3	1.2
2	Carrot (<i>Daucus carota</i>)	5.3 ± 0.5	1.3	5.35 ± 1.0	1.5
3	Ginger (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	3.2 ± 0.3	1.2	3.6 ± 0.8	1.3
4	Potato (<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>)	0.52 ± 0.08	1.2	0.525 ± 0.1	1.3
5	Tomato (<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>)	3.0 ± 0.1	1.4	3.10 ± 0.1	1.5
6	Cauliflower (<i>Brassica oleracea</i>)	0.15 ± 0.08	1.0	0.15 ± 0.08	1.2
7	Cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i>)	0.82 ± 0.1	1.5	0.85 ± 0.15	1.6

^aAverage of five replicate analyses of each sample.

^bThe measure of precision is the relative standard deviation (RSD).

Determination of cadmium in some fertilizer samples

1.0 g of finely grounded fertilizer sample was accurately weighed and dissolved in 5 mL of concentrated HNO₃ acid in a 100-mL micro-Kjeldahl flask by gently heating. Then it was diluted with de-ionized water. The solution was filtered and neutralized by dilute NH₄OH solution in the presence of 1-2 mL of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The content of the flask was filtered and transferred quantitatively into 25-mL flask. The resulting solution was then filtered and diluted up to the mark with de-ionized water. A suitable aliquot (1-2 mL) of the final solution was pipetted out into a 10-mL calibrated flask and the Cadmium content was determined as described under Procedure using tartrate or EDTA as a masking agent. The results are shown in **Table 10**. The highest value of cadmium was found in TSP (Triple superphosphate). From the study, it is observed that high cadmium content is found in low quality in TSP fertilizer. For this reason Bangladesh rice has an average of 0.099 mg of cadmium per kg. It is more dangerous for Bangladesh as most of her people eat 400-500 grams of rice each day. Cadmium contamination in Bangladesh rice is massive due to the usage of low quality of imported TSP fertilizers.

Table 10. Determination of cadmium in some fertilizer samples.

Sample	Fertilizers	Concentration/(mg kg ⁻¹)	
		Found ^a (n=5)	RSD (%)
1	Urea	1.8 ± 0.3	1.5
2	T.S.P (Triple SuperPhosphate)	20.5 ± 1.0	2.5
3	MOP (Muriate of Potash)	15.2 ± 0.5	2.0

^a Average of five replicate determinations ±s

Determination of cadmium in some surface soil samples

An air-dried homogenized soil sample (10 g) was accurately weighed and placed in a 100-mL micro-kjeldahl flask. The sample was digested in the presence of an oxidizing agent following a

method recommended by Jackson (Jackson, 1958). The contents of the flask were filtered through a Whatman No. 40 filter paper into 25- mL calibrated flask and neutralized with dilute NH₄OH solution in the presence of 1-2 mL of 0.01% (w/v) EDTA solution. The resulting solution was then diluted up to the mark with deionized water.

A suitable aliquot (1-2 mL) of the final solution was pipetted out into a 10-mL calibrated flask and the cadmium content was determined as described under Procedure using tartrate or EDTA as a masking agent. The cadmium content was then determined by the above procedure and quantified from a calibration graph prepared concurrently. The results are shown in **Table 11**. The average value of cadmium in Bangladesh surface soil was found to be 2.65mg kg⁻¹. The results of the highest value of cadmium found in BSRM (Bangladesh Steel Re-rolling Mills Ltd., Chittagong, Bangladesh) soil because Cd-amalgam was used in Steel Re-rolling Mills to join the iron rod. This film of cadmium was also applied on ferrous metal surfaces to retard corrosion by an electroplating technique. The lowest value of cadmium was obtained in the marine soil which was diluted with seawater. The normal value was obtained from agriculture soil which is useful for normal crop cultivation.

Table 11. Determination of cadmium in some surface soil samples

Cadmium			
Serial No.	(mg kg⁻¹)^a	RSD (%)	Sample Source^b
(n=5)			
S ₁ ^b	0.45±0.05	1.2	Agriculture soil (Chittagong University Campus)
S ₂	0.31±0.08	1.5	Marine soil (Bay of Bengal)
S ₃	1.8±0.09	1.8	Traffic soil

			(Kadamtali Bus Terminal)
S ₄	2.5±0.5	2.0	Industrial soil (Eastern cables)
S ₅	3.2±0.8	2.5	Industrial soil (T.S.P. Complex Chittagong)
S ₆	9.5±1.0	2.8	Industrial soil (Bangladesh Steel Re-rolling Mills Ltd., Chittagong, Bangladesh)
S ₇	0.78±0.3	2.5	Road-side soil (Dhaka-Chittagong Highway)

^a Average of five analyses of each sample.

^b Composition of the soil samples: C, N, P, K, Na, Ca, Mg, Cu, Mo, Fe, Mn, Pb, V, Zn, Cd, Co, NO₃, SO₄, etc.

Conclusions

In this paper, a new, simple, sensitive, selective and inexpensive method with the Cd-morin complex was developed successfully for the determination of cadmium in some real, environmental, biological, tobacco, food, vegetable, fertilizer, and soil samples, for continuous monitoring to establish the trace levels of cadmium in different sample matrices. Although many sophisticated techniques such as pulse polarography, HPLC, NAA, AAS, ICP-OES, and ICP-MS are available for the determination of cadmium at ultra-trace levels in numerous complex materials, factors such as the low cost of the instrument, easy handling, portable, lack of requirement for consumables and almost no maintenance have caused spectrofluorimetric to remain a popular technique, particularly in laboratories of developing countries with limited budget. The sensitivity in terms of fluorescence intensity and precision in terms of relative standard

deviation (0-3%) of the present method are very reliable for the determination of cadmium in real samples down to pg g^{-1} (10^{-12}g g^{-1}) levels in aqueous medium at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$).

References

- Ahmed, M. J., Zannat, T., & Fatema, Z. 2014. A Simple Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Trace Level of Cadmium in Real, Environmental, Biological, Tobacco, Fertilizer and Soil Samples Using 2', 3, 4', 5, 7 Pentahydroxyflavone. *American Chemical Science Journal*, 4(4): 481-503.
- Christensen, F. & Olson, E. 1957. Cadmium Poisoning. Report of a Fatal Case, with Discussion of Pathology and Clinical Aspects. *Arch. Indust. Health*. 16(1): 8-13.
- Fergusson, J. E. 1990. Heavy elements: chemistry, environmental impact and health effects: Pergamon, Oxford. p.548.
- Gao, J., Zhao, G., & Kang, J. 1995. The application of trimesic acid to the determination of terbium by spectrofluorimetry. *Talanta*. 42(10): 1497-1503.
- Greenberg, A. E., Clesceri, L. S., & Eaton, A. D. 1992. Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater: American Public Health Association, Washington, D.C. p.3-82.
- Threshold limit values for chemical substances and physical agents and biological exposure indices. 1996. American Council for Government Industrial Hygiene (ACGIH).
- Jackson, M. 1958. Soil chemical analysis prentice Hall. Inc., Englewood Cliffs, NJ. 498: 272.
- Job, P. 1928. Formation and stability of inorganic complexes in solution. 9: 113.
- Kjellström, T., Friberg, L., & Rahnster, B. 1979. Mortality and cancer morbidity among cadmium-exposed workers. *Environmental health perspectives*, 28: 199-204.
- Mitchell Perry Jr, H., & Yunice, A. 1965. Acute pressor effects of intra-arterial cadmium and mercuric ions in anesthetized rats. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology, and Medicine*, 120(3): 805-808.
- Mukherji, A. 1970. Analytical Chemistry of Zirconium and Hafnium. 1st ed. Pergamon Press, New York. p.385.
- Nielsen, F. H. 1984. Ultratrace elements in nutrition. *Annual review of nutrition*. 4(1): 21-41.
- Ojeda, C. B., De Torres, A. G., Rojas, F. S., & Pavon, J. C. 1987. Fluorimetric determination of trace amounts of gallium in biological tissues. *Analyst*. 112(11): 1499-1501.

- Pal, B. K. & Chaudhury, B. 1985. Triazene-N-oxides as new type of fluorimetric reagents. *Microchimica Acta*. 85(5-6): 437-446.
- Pal, B. K., Kabiraj, U., & Ukiluddin, M. 1987. Fluorimetric use of morin in the ultra-trace determination of cadmium and its application to sewage sludge analyses. *Analyst*. 112(2): 171-174.
- Pal, B. K., Singh, K. A., & Dutta, K. 1992. Spectrofluorimetric determination of molybdenum in some real and environmental samples. *Talanta*. 39(8): 971-975.
- Parker, G. A. 1986. Molybdenum Anthropogenic Compounds. Springer, Berlin. p. 217-240.
- Schroeder, H. 1971. Trace elements in the human environment. *Ecologist*. 1: 11.
- Stahr, H. 1991. Analytical methods in toxicology: Wiley, New York.
- Sun, Y., Yang, J., & Tzeng, S. 1999. Rapid determination of molybdate in natural waters by coprecipitation and neutron activation analysis. *Analyst*. 124(3): 421-424.
- Vogel, A. I. & Jeffery, G. 1989. Vogel's textbook of quantitative chemical analysis: Wiley, New York.
- Yoe, J., & Jones, A. 1944. Stability constant of coordination compounds. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* 16:11.

Dr. M. Jamaluddin Ahmed, *FRSC*

Professor Ahmed is a Bangladeshi citizen, born at Brahmanbaria in 1955. He has a bright academic and professional career. He started his professional career in the Department of Chemistry, Chittagong University as a Lecturer since 1st April, 1981. He has been appointed as a Professor of Chemistry in 1995. Prof. Ahmed obtained his PhD degree in Analytical Chemistry from Jadavpur University, India in 1990 under the Govt. of India Scholarship Scheme. He worked as a postdoctoral fellow in Analytical Chemistry with Prof. R.M. Smith of Loughborough University on a Commonwealth Fellowship (2000-2001) and this was followed with Prof. M. I. Karayannis, University of Ioannina, Greece(1995-1996), with Prof. Michael Moore, Director, National Research Centre for Environmental Toxicology, of The Queensland University, Australia(1997) on a Commonwealth Science Council Fellowship and Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing(2006 & 2009) on a CAS-TWAS Fellowship.

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

